

THE ROLE OF CREATIVITY IN THE SPIRIT OF NURTURING SPIRITUAL TRADITIONS OF THE PEOPLE.

Fergana region Altyaryk
district 39-music secondary
school science teachers
handbook to be one of the
culture of
Ismoilova Dilnoza
Nematovna

Annotation. With this article will embody spiritual traditions of the content that we have all the types of educational folk art, its place, its our people, amo, melodies, words, song, term, lap, dance - tunes it was believed that it was created in harmony with dance, performance, music spectacle.

Keywords. Primitiv is magic, proverb, metho, life, tradition, rita, holiday, work, syncretic, everyday life, mixing, events.

Nurturing the spiritual traditions of men in the spirit of folk music the art of creativity of the people that appear in the game, from primitive people to be a part of the method, jodi aytim of people singing and musical tunes ranging from the sound signal from the form, as usual, are widely used. Other muchfolklore from the types compress, basically, living the process of the ritual, the ceremony, were separated with directly tied to the holiday. Folk have most musicent elegant pure samples not in the sense of events, household daily life, work, ceremony, will find the art form that the decision as the performance of its duties. Many people sinkretik samples of music, that is, if the form is mixed in them tone-tone, words, songs, football, my lap, the cancer game-dance tunes, and the art of tracking, with

the combination of activated without watching musical will occur. Certain artistic traditions, and form, for example, based on a template samples of music in people's tone various times and circumstances, for example, the composition of the audience or the performers of execution time, place and will change depending on the environment. Therefore, there will be a few samples each in the form of musical folklore. People use music in regional, national and local separate the styling, for example in the music of the people of bukhara, uzbekistan-Samarkand, Fergana-tashkent, kashkadarya and surkhandarya and Kashkadarya music style.

Spiritual traditions in the spirit of nurturing creativity badi samples of peopleiy epic in terms of content, i.e. national, a musical fairy tale, maddohlik, qissaxonlik, sing like a legend, dramatic, music lyrics and watch that, that song is in my lap, yalla, starter type, depending on conditions play - personal, ceremonial songs, labor songs of a special place. Samples of the people of the people's music, that is, the completion of the construction of public life as the artistic mind living alone, without amateur singer, including go'yanda, halfa, continues to do'mbrakash is that, like dutorchi, as well as by collective ensemble or in a way that is executed. People are the basis of the style of music, national music, composer and composers of creativity, is an important source of popular music. Creativity in turn people, excellent music with the art of closely develops in mutual contact. The people's charged in the current period, samples of ancient music, and the changes in the sameningdek, on the basis of them, but new ones are created. Music musical instruments a diversity of people. Them a ring, for example, qo'muz in kyrgyzstan, ukraine and busy inra or old historical-cultural communication of various nations, for example, Uzbek, Tajik, uighur, turkmenistan, karakalpaks in dutar can be related.

The ancient ceremony of the feast of the uzbekistan people's creativity from the national dress of February, people draw from the customs, songs, music, and

baxshichilik his let's let qiziqchi, dance arts, practical arts, in general, the various appearances of folklorning find the content requested. At the same time, people have a direct impact in the creation of amateur creativity, it can also enrich, and also has been developing. Folklore from people in their place amateur amateur spread wide use in the creation of gaining more momentum among the public caused. The people of uzbekistan from not only amateur sarchashmasi di, but also is continuously advancing our literature and the arts. On the basis of artistic creativity or poems tales about people taking the pictures show the movies knew large-small, equally the attention of yu gets pulled. Nurturing creativity in the spirit of the spiritual traditions of men the people of the past resonance imaging did not only remain, but also yangroq the voice of the current period. His insightful people of creativity-stained, soda and beauty at the same time with ba, which organized the creation of the public holiday in the holiday and di amateur enrich the content of the event, and did not remain bezabgina, but other kinds of writing, literature and art, in general, has a great social impact in our marriage. This doubtlessly, national folklorning spiritual, cultural and educational role in life requires more thoughtful will need further analysis.

Antique-turkic peoples from ancient times, including the wedding of uzbekistan, in our-in ceremony poets, further, the singers, this chilar, polvon the masharabozlar, the dancer, the dorboz, the qo'g'irchoqboz between creative competitions, mushoira, baxribayt, aytishuv through traditional historical sources we know. Our people are dos-tone tale-cho'pchak in song, in poetry, humor-mutoyiba, the game of their traditions the cancer of human history, manifesting feelings of come. The ancient turkic peoples in the creation of oral analysis of various aspects of life, it is not possible to ilg'ab the expression of human labour and dreams and hope. The people in them social, spiritual traditions, and high expression of the ideacan be seen. The process of labor and chief of the tradition of the relations of man is the source. Ijti folk traditions of moi the essence of

mankind the period known it in outlook, dreams and aspirations. lifestyle daily life of the members of summarizing the expression. The good and bad events happen in human life, first of all, the people is manifested in their creation.

Amateur creativity now increasingly developing new form of content and it's coming professional, above all, the creativity of its people, closely associated with folklore traditions should give you a wider understanding to the side. Because, amateur even in ancient times, now and then, basically, due to the popularity of folk traditions they will find you. The business of life style of people, first of all, family. Also, it is known that all the family system is the basis of society. Creative family in this context-the social importance of how important the event is to admit and realize that it is necessary. Consequently, a wider social phenomenon should be looking out as an amateur. At the formation of the active social person, in particular in the organization of meaningful leisure time the person amateur-select state budget great importance. Cultural and educational institutions, as well as in the production of household, living in a place to live, especially in family event-amateur spread wide, which find their expression gaining momentum in the world of amateur artistic shows that important social phenomenon.

The end of the 80s of the twentieth century-and 90-the start of the year in our country, the interaction of artistic traditions amateur family re-boost. In the scene shown to the broad masses of cultural and educational events has been. Thus, the family of all times, in all social systems, respectable, that is the basis of all society social colossal structure are indicative of how important her own. Everyone, the people of the nation an identity, first of all in the family was known. His human life, struggle, pursue joy-joy and grieving wealth, resonance-imaging is mean. In addition, the specific encyclopedia of the philosophy of the east "Qobusnoma"as noted at the family, the education of the span of the nation, the knowledge is the school of wisdom. Also, at the same time, the family is the

mirror of society in the public therefore also associated with the family of our people, bright events of any serious preparation for her umidvorlik look from him and it is no coincidence that ancient tantanavor be held with strong beliefs. Therefore, in this case the creativity of interest to further strengthen the family, to give him more attention and deep, is the motivation of enhancing its position, of course. Thus, in our country, which is held on a regular basis and go further-poets, this a-qiziqchi, amateur and artistic people, in particular, folk-ethnography of the contest of the pile and family plays an important role. People of the public to be the direct organizer of amateur artistic cultural and educational institutions should also serve to help the working people in meaningful leisure time. As it is known, all types of artistic creation, including people belonging to the people in the family pile, creative songs, music, dance and other art is of particular importance. Any period of people's artist of uzbekistan to the person in society, always has been companion. After all the difficult and joyful times of the people any of the songs in their heart longing-longing-of-the-world expression. Uzbekistan the family of artistic creativity in the folk song-the art of chilik a separate profession. The majority of the creativity involved with the family on track in this genre identified.

Songs of the people living there are two major factors. The first one is that the most important truth of life reflected in them. Their marriage is at the heart of the trade no later than those from the beginning of the experiences that created the event-of sorrow, of xasrat, bright and think mayus-the song of the idea in the world-considered a fantasy tone. In the present day some “songs” creativity ethical-spiritual beautiful, it will be good if you could sign teranlik committed. The people in the song, thus meekness wealth to human vitality, the kind of light is dedicated to the soul has with the audience, they hear again and again is what comes next. This song is never the character without losing the value of his art.

Secondly, people in the song, the simplicity of the elegant form of

expression of the essential and profound, which rom are beautiful, stand out with the glamorous. But, come from ancient times to the present day in uzbekistan, which has begun by our grandpa family tunes, folk songs, alla, and almost being forgotten yalla go because of my lap. Previously, each household in our national musical dutar doira, qashqar rubob osig'lib in the wall of tunes perfectly executing our national standing and the owners of the house they also included. His grandmother by our fail-in the form of advice, said the song has a direct impact on the minds of our children.

Dear friends, as you know, is of particular importance in nurturing the spiritual state of the music man. But today, the family has been to strengthen in europe to emulate. Course conducted in the republic in the celebration of the variety of folk songs, it has become a tradition to customize performance. Their impact on our lifestyle this national madaniyatimizga does not remain after kursatma and spiritual. Therefore, in the family, educational institutions specialised in music and art, common-school education to children from the age of the sample of the creativity of people in the present day with the combination of various songs eshitilayotgan case, we must teach. Of course, we should deliver to the younger generation without losing the purity of ancient tone, then the values of people's creativity and ma'na we onlyviy, which is our heritage, our traditions and we can deliver from generation to generation to their mode.

It should be noted that people's unique creativity of samples, preservation of traditions and schools for specific performance, the development system was created. The national art center museum of uzbekistan and the status has been established, the status of once every two years the international art and arts festival to be held in the international conference baxshichilik the prestige of our unique heritage in the world will serve as a practical step in the way of significant increase in all sizes. The development of such practical people that have been a festival of creativity has an important role in the genre's. Including:

- to improve the quality of cultural services to the population, cultural satisfy their needs provide a meaningful transition of the head and empty the pros and the creative team of national values, customs and traditions of the program embodies the model of the formation;

- people's xavaskorlik the preservation and development of art and artistic creativity, and artistic amaliy creative teams to create favorable conditions to maintain their organization and functioning of the group, amateur, and the process of creation of matter enriched go on a systematic basis;

- a circle of children to attract a matter of learning foreign languages, and “speech culture” of the course on the organization, the people's creativity all genres and directions, and to promote the intangible cultural heritage of arts and original amateur holicha wide to deliver to future generations;

- literature and art figures and professional group of creative, spiritual, educational, cultural and public events organization of them, the participation of the population, in particular, in the day of the interview directly with youth meetings and round artisticzish;

- the choice, the people's creativity and the art of tracking in the district (city) level, the conduct of the festival, identify talented young people, support of creative young people;

- the celebration of the mass, and people watching is one of the main tasks of organization of the holiday festival.

The implementation of these tasks absorption into the minds of the people in national and universal values of our youth, cultural and ethnic traditions to the preservation and on this basis without the support of the creative potential of the youth people's creativity is to create the conditions necessary for the production of ruyobga. The status of the state of creativity in people of our state to the art and culture as the point of attention attention and care can be assessed. The creativity of the youth of our country's people will not have imagine without perfect

information. The traditional culture of every nation of history, and above all, his creation - in folk art, a poem, a poem of epic and embodied in if they are to realize the identity of the nation, its specific national values, traditions in the preservation and development of an invaluable resource.

REFERENCES

1. Kholmatova, Z. T., & Kholikova, D. M. (2022). MODEL OF DEVELOPING AND DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 190-195.
2. Dilobarkhon, K. (2019). The importance of modern innovation in education. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
3. Kholikova, D. (2020). INTELLECTUAL ACTIVITY OF CREATIVE THINKING VERBAL TEST “UNUSUAL USE”. *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES*, 22.
4. Maxsitovna, K. D. (2022). Pedagogical Problems of Child Raising in the Uzbek Family. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 542-546.
5. Xolmatova, Z. T., & Xolikova, D. M. (2022). TALABALARDA INNOVASION FIKRLASH KO‘NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MODELI. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 139-144.
6. Холикова, Д. (2021). Возможности диагностики эффективности компенсационного подхода в обучении. *Общество и инновации*, 2(9/S), 239-252.
7. Kholikova, D. M. (2021). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF INCREASING INNOVATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 422-424.

8. Kholikova, D. M. (2021). DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 549-552.
9. O.Erkaboyev, D.Tursunova. Aqliy tarbiyasini shakllantirishda sharq allomalari qarashlaridan foydalanish . PEDAGOG, 2023. 59-61
- 10.O.Erkaboyev. O'smirlarni armiya safida xizmat qilishga tayyorlash bosqichida jismoniy tarbiya va chaqiruvga qadar boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik integratsiyasi. Ta'lim fidoyilari, 2022. 73-79
- 11.Khalilovich, N. E., & Alijonovna, N. G. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF RECYCLING NATURAL RESOURCES. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
- 12.Нажмиддинов, Э., & Мухамедиев, М. (2023). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
- 13.Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., & Мухаммадиев, М. А. (2022). ФАРҒОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИНИНГ ТУР ТАРКИБИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 60-68.
- 14.Нажмиддинов, Э. Х. (2022). ФАРҒОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 189-194.
- 15.Najmiddinov, E. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NATURE IN THE FORMATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE IDEAL GENERATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 149-154.
- 16.Najmiddinov, E. (2022). " ICHTHYOLOGY AND HYDROBIOLOGY" PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 152-160.

- 17.Kholmatova, Z. T. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF GENDER ASPECTS OF EDUCATION. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 60-65.
- 18.Kholmatova, Z. T., & Kholikova, D. M. (2022). MODEL OF DEVELOPING AND DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE THINKING SKILLS IN STUDENTS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 190-195.
- 19.Xolmatova, Z. T., & Xolikova, D. M. (2022). TALABALARDA INNOVASION FIKRLASH KO'NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MODELI. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 139-144.
- 20.Kholmatova, Z., & Axmadaliyeva, M. (2022). Healthy lifestyle (HLS)-The basis of valeology in kindergarten. *Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research*, 11(9), 136-139.
- 21.Kholmatova, Z., & Olamnazarova, F. (2022). Problems of the communicational approach of language teaching in the primary class. *Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research*, 11(9), 140-144.
- 22.Tillavoldievna, K. Z. (2022). Problems of Family Education in People's Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 535-541.
- 23.Холматова, З. Т. (2022). ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ГЕНДЕРЛИ ЁНДАШУВ ДАВР ТАЛАБИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(3), 134-140.
- 24.Tillavoldievna, K. Z. (2022). Problems of Family Education in People's Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 535-541.
- 25.Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.

26. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
27. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
28. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGUISTICS AND THE HISTORY OF ITS ANALYTICAL DEVELOPMENT. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 99-105.
29. Vosiljonov, A., & Isaqova, X. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(2).
30. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIY PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
31. Nabijonova, F. (2022). Boshlangich sinflarda didaktik oyinlarning ahamiyati: Nabijonova Feruza. *Qo'qon universitetining ilmiy materiallar bazasi*, 1(000006).
32. Dilfuza, S., Nabijonova, F., & Matlubaxon, A. (2022). TA'LIM VA O'QITISH NAZARIYASINING MUHIM JIHLTLARI. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 2(19), 366-372.
33. Nabijonova, F. (2022). BOSHLANGICH SINFLARDA OZGA GAPNING QOLLANILISHI. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 2(19), 180-184.
34. НАБИЖОНОВА, Ф. ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ. *ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ Учредители: ООО "Институт управления и социально-экономического развития"*, (10), 90-92.
35. Feruza, N. (2023). Characteristics of the Lessons of the Native Language. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 32-36.

- 36.Набижонова, Ф. (2022). ОНА ТИЛИ ВА АДАБИЁТ ТАЪЛИМИНИНГ ТАРИХИ ВА ТАРАҚҚИЁТ ЙЎЛЛАРИ. *Мировая наука*, (10 (67)), 38-41.
- 37.Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2022). ORIGIN AND CONCEPT OF TABOO VOCABULARY. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(10), 184-190.
- 38.Yulchiboyeva, L. Q. (2022). IRIM-SIRIM BILAN BOG ‘LIQ TIL BIRLIKLARINING TAHLILIIY O ‘RGANILISHI. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 170-175.
- 39.Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2022). Identification And Education Of Gifted Children. *Asia Pacific Journal Of Marketing & Management Review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 42-47.
- 40.Gulnoza, R., & Lola, K. (2022). Obrazlar Talqinida Lingvistik Imkoniyatlar. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 91-95.
- 41.Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.
- 42.Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO ‘LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.
- 43.Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE’RIYATIDA “SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.
- 44.Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.
- 45.Kipchakova, Y. (2021). METHODOLOGICAL AND DIDACTIC ASPECTS OF INFORMATION AND INTELLECTUAL CULTURE IN THE

EDUCATION OF A DEVELOPED GENERATION. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 156-159.

46. Kipchakova, Y. X., & Kodirova, G. A. (2020). INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5), 29-31.
47. KIPCHAKOVA, Y., ABDUXAMIDOVA, M., & RAXMONALIYEVA, M. THE IMPACT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *СТУДЕНЧЕСКИЙ ВЕСТНИК Учредители: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью "Интернаука"*, 37-38.
48. Қипчақова, Ё., Махмудова, М., & Умарова, З. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР МЕҲНАТИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (22-7), 9-10.
49. Қипчақова, Ё., Соибжонова, Ш., & Абдуқаюмова, С. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА СОҒЛОМ ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (22-7), 11-12.
50. Iminov, B. B. (2020). INNOVATIVE CULTURAL LINKS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(3), 263-270.
51. Iminov, B. B. (2019). A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO INNOVATIVE AND CULTURAL-RELATIONS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(5), 157-162.
52. Gayratovich, M. E., Jahongir, M., & Musajonovna, A. F. (2022). SPELEOTOURISTIC POSSIBILITIES OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 66-70.

53. Mamatisakov, J. (2022). 1 Òzbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (2000-2005) 2 Ziyo. uz (sayti). *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 587-590.
54. Mamatisakov, J., Egamberdi, B., & Dostonbek, M. (2022). TERRITORIAL ASPECTS OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF ETHNOONYMS OF FERGANA REGION. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 591-595.
55. Mamatisakov, J. (2022). IMPROVING STUDENTS' GEOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE BY SCHOOL GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(10), 88-94.
56. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
57. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
58. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
59. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О ‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.
60. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o‘g‘li. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
61. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.

62. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1039-1044.
63. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(02), 89-96.
64. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. *Innovation In The Modern Education System*, 2(18), 183-189.
65. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.
66. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.
67. To‘lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
68. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To‘lqinovna (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
69. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.

70. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
71. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
72. Karimovich, U. R., Mamasodikovna, N. M., & Abdullaevich, E. A. (2021). The Role and Importance of Music Clubs in The Leisure of Young People. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 2(2), 47-49.
73. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 51-53).
74. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 51-53).
75. Ulugbek, R. (2021, January). AN ANALYSIS OF WORDS WHOSE EMOTIONAL MEANING CHANGES IN MODERN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. In *Euro-Asia Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 131-136).
76. Kakharovna, A. M., Tadjimatovich, Y. M., Rakhmatovich, S. O., & Mirzahamdamovna, Q. B. (2021). Modern Approaches to the Teaching of Fine Arts. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 4250-4254.
77. Ahmedbekova, M. (2022). ЁШ АВЛОДНИНГ БАДИИЙ-ЭСТЕТИК ИЖОДКОРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ТАСВИРИЙ САНЪАТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДАГИ ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 112-119.

78. Maxpuzakhon, A. (2022). Methods of Using Modern Pedagogical Technologies in Organizing Fine Arts Lessons. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 268-271.
79. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 914-917.
80. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1040-1044.
81. Alimjanova, M. (2021). About Gender Stereotypes. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning*, 2(6), 1-5.
82. Yunusovna, A. M. (2021). Pedagogical system of responsibility formation in primary school students based on national staff. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(06), 1-7.
83. Gulnoza, R., & Lola, K. (2022). Obrazlar Talqinida Lingvistik Imkoniyatlar. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 91-95.
84. Sohiba, Z., & Gulnoza, R. (2022). LINGVOKULTUROLOGIYADA “SOG’INCH” KONSEPTINING QO’LLANILISHI VA O’ZIGA XOSLIKLARI. *O’ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(8), 711-717.
85. Sohiba, Z., & Gulnoza, R. (2022). MATNLARDA OBRAZLAR SILSILASI VA ULARNING LINGVOPRAGMATIK TALQINI. *O’ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(9), 366-369.
86. Gulnoza, R., & Madinabonu, I. (2022). XALQ OG’ZAKI IJODIDA “SHAXS” SEMASINING OYDINLASHUVI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 98-108.

- 87.Sobirovna, U. O. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA YANGI DARSLIK VA ERISHILGAN NATIJA. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 230-234.
- 88.Sobirovna, U. O. (2022). NATIONAL CURRICULUM AND NEW GENERATION MOTHER TONGUE AND READING TEXTBOOK. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(10), 176-183.
- 89.Usmanova, O. S. (2022). A TEXTBOOK ON NATIVE LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY, CREATED ON THE BASIS OF THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 48-54.
- 90.Sobirovna, U. O. (2022). The Use of Mnemo Technique in the Textbook of Primary School Native Language and Reading Literacy. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 17, 421-426.
- 91.Усмонова, О. (2022). РИВОЖЛАНГАН МАМЛАКАТЛАРДА ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИ. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 148-158.
- 92.Sobirovna, U. O. (2022). The Use of Mnemotechniques in Teaching Younger Schoolchildren. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 446-450.
- 93.Исроилова, С. М., & Мадумарова, М. Д. (2022). ПОИСК НАИБОЛЕЕ ОПТИМАЛЬНЫХ СПОСОБОВ ИНТЕНСИФИКАЦИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (1 (157)), 8-14.
- 94.Исраилова, С. М., & Мадумарова, М. Д. (2019). Исторические предпосылки типологических исследований. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (12-2 (145)), 121-123.

95. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
96. Мирзабоев, Й. А. (2022). Тур Ўзгариш Чизиклари Учта Бўлган, Гиперболик Қисмларининг Ҳаммаси Харақтеристик Учбурчаклардан Иборат Бўлган Бешбурчакли Соҳада Учинчи Тартибли Кўринишдаги Параболик-Гиперболик Тенглама Учун Битта Чегаравий Масала Ҳақида. *Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research*, 1(5), 363-366.
97. MIRZABOYEV, Y. BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QITUVCHILARINING MATEMATIKA O 'QITISH METODIKASI. O 'RTA UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA MATEMATIKA O 'QITISHNING MAQSADI. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 169-172.
98. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada*.
99. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.
100. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.
101. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.
102. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE NEED TO IMPROVE HUMAN'S NOOSPHERICAL RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 *Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 23-30.

103. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING PERSONAL ECOLOGICAL CULTURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 5-12.
104. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). АТРОФ-МУҲИТНИ АСРАШ БЎЙИЧА МИЛЛИЙ СТРАТЕГИК РЕЖА ВА УНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 251-258.
105. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). ЯНГИ ТАРАҚҚИЁТ БОСҚИЧИДА ЭКОЛОГИК МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ДАСТУРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 1179-1186.
106. Абдумаликов, А. А. (2019). Human and Natural Harmony in the Historical Process. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 205-209.
107. Abidzhanovich, A. A. (2020). Issues Of Formation Of Rationality In Relations Of Nature With Society. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 301-304.
108. Abdumalikov, A. A. (2019). Environmental Ecological Policy in Uzbekistan and Necessity Of Formation Of Rational Communication To Nature. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(9), 94-101.
109. Soliyev, A. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИ ТАРБИЯЛАНУВЧИЛАРИ ОНГИДА МИЛЛИЙ МУСИҚИЙ ОНАНГЛАРГА МОЙИЛЛИКНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА МИЛЛИЙ ЧОЛГ 'УЛАРНИНГ О'РНИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(1), 637-646.
110. Раҳмонов, У. К., & Солиев, А. Р. (2022). СОЗАНДАЛИК САЊАТИНИНГ БАРМОҚДАГИ НОЛАЛАРИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 109-119.

111. Солиев, А. (2022). БАТАН ТУЙҒУСИ. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 5(2), 120-123.
112. Солиев, А., Аблязов, Д., & Тўланов, Б. (2022). МУСИҚА ТАЪЛИМИДА КОМПЬЮТЕР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 2(19), 207-211.
113. Sayidolimov, J. B. O. G. L. (2023). AGIOGRAFIK OBRAZLARNING MAZMUN-MOHİYATIDAGI EVRILISHLAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(3), 1318-1322.